

CLINICAL DESCRIPTION OF ADULT PATIENTS WITH ACQUIRED HEART DEFECTS

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Annotation. All patients studied should be given a clinical description of these patients in order to assess the immune status, to conduct a comparative study of the indicators of the immune system. This study made it possible to obtain complete information on its condition at the time of assessment of the immune status of the object, specific features in the course of the disease, the basics of differential diagnostics on differentiation from one another, the results of laboratory and instrumental examinations, treatment tactics.

Key otters: immune system, diagnosis, labarator, complaints

In the diagnosis of diseases studied, as in all pathologies, it is important to study the complaint of patients. For this reason, all patient (N=120) complaints were studied to the study, the results obtained were brought in the form of Table 3.1. When all complaints were interpreted and analyzed, it was observed that they did not always occur, did not always bother patients. For this reason, patients did not form them as complaints of illness and did not see a doctor.

When referring to generalized numbers on complaints indicated by patients, the leadership among patient complaints has naturally been attributed to general malaise (100.0%, n=120), as overall malaise develops in the body as a result of heart defects negatively affecting cardiac activity.

Other specific symptoms that followed were leg edema (90.83±2.63%, n=109) and rapid fatigue (88.33±2.93%, n=106). These symptoms were also characteristic of this disease and were characterized by a high incidence among patients. The presence of pain in the legs of patients, the observation of whining symptoms, was also observed in most patients - 87.50±3.02% (n=105) and 86.67±3.10% (n=104), respectively. The high incidence of these symptoms has also shown that they are a specific symptom characteristic of this disease.

Table 3.1

Complaints from patients who had side effects, N=120

Complaints	Мутлоқ сон	Нисбий сон, %
General weakness	120	100,0
Leg swelling	109	90,83±2,63
Quick fatigue	106	88,33±2,93
Leg pain	105	87,50±3,02

Hansirash	100	86,67±3,10
Heart rate (tachycardia)	91	75,80±3,91
Back pain	83	69,17±4,22
Reduced urine volume	70	58,33±4,50
Body temperature rise	69	57,50±4,51
Dizziness	104	83,30±3,40
Shortness of breath	58	48,30±4,56
Arm-leg bruise	54	45,00±4,54
Pain in the heart area	41	34,17±4,33
Headache	20	16,67±3,40
Numbness	7	5,80±2,14
Hair loss	6	5,00±1,99

It was also characterized by symptoms such as dizziness, tachycardia, back pain, decreased urine volume, increased body temperature occurring in more than half of the patients studied.

Their total was found in 57.50±4.51% to 83.30±3.40% of cases in patients. Other symptoms were characterized by low incidence compared to those cited above, and were found in 5.00±48.30% of total studied.

Thus, a study of patient complaints diagnosed with acquired heart defects found that symptoms specific to this pathology were naturally multiple, exemplified by general weakness (100%), leg swelling (90.83%), rapid fatigue (88.33%). Some symptoms were relatively rare-tachycardia (75.80%), back pain (69.17%), decreased urine content (58.33%), and increased body temperature (57.50%). The remaining symptoms were described as occurring in 5.00-48.30% of cases. Along with the complaints brought by patients, their objective examination also plays an important role, for this reason in this chapter we found it necessary to cite the degree of occurrence of the main characters in the objective examination. The results obtained were presented in Table 3.2.

Table 3.2.

Results of an objective Courier of patients diagnosed with heart defects, n=120

The main characters in the objective examination		Absolute number (%)	relative number (%)
On the limbs	Pain	117	97,50±1,43
	Shish	112	93,30±2,28
	Local temperature	62	51,70±4,56

Decreased vesicular breathing	82	68,30±4,25
Acrosianosis	81	67,50±4,28
Pulsation in the veins of the neck	71	59,17±4,48
The movement is bounded	64	53,30±4,55
Exudative-proliferative changes	47	39,20±4,46
Thinness	40	30,80±4,22
Peripheral muscle atrophy	10	8,33±2,52

From the cited table 3.2, it was noted that the lens had the highest incidence of pain and swelling in the groin limbs-97.50±1.43% (n=117) and 93.30±2.28% (n=112), respectively. These indicators were properly proportional to patient complaints, reaffirming that they were specific symptoms. The objective examination also revealed other specific signs in patients, which were found in 39.20-68.30% of cases. The least identified signs were thinness and peripheral muscle atrophy (30.80±4.22%, N=40 and 8.33±2.52%, n=10, respectively), indicating that these patients were not in critical condition.

If we see the general condition of these patients, a satisfactory condition was found in 2 patients (1.67±1.17%), a moderate-severity condition was found in 117 patients (97.50±1.43%), no acute-condition patient was identified.

Thus, the results of an objective examination of patients with heart defects showed that in most cases, pain in the limbs (97.50%) and swelling (93.30%) as well as decreased vesicular breathing (68.30%) as well as acrocyanosis (67.50%) were observed. It is a notable case that the extent to which these signs occur is properly porportsional to the state of detection of patient complaints. The fact that the bulk of patients are in moderate-to-severe condition (97.50%) is one of the main signs that all groups are representative, making it possible to obtain truthful results.

We also found it necessary to cite the results of auscultation of the heart in the process of objective vision. The results of auscultation in patients are varied and the results are shown in Table 3.3.

Table 3.3.

Results of auscultation of patients diagnosed with heart defects, n=120

Auscultation tones in the heart	Absolute number relative number (%)	Absolute number relative number (%)

Systole-diastolic noise	99	82,50±3,47
2-Tone Accent in the lungs	97	80,83±3,59
Tone 1 relegated	73	60,83±4,46
Decreased heart tone	27	22,50±3,81
Tone 1 increased	14	11,67±2,93
Valve prosthetic noise	12	10,00±2,74

From the cited table 3.3, the results of auscultation in the objective vision process were met to varying degrees (10.00±2.74% to 82.50±3.47%), when patients were transported a different nosological unit parnik (yuan, Yumn, load, and an) combined into a group of heart defects. However, it is worth saying that auscultation is still one of the important clinical examination methods that assess cardiac activity today.

In addition to clinical-objective examination methods, we have used restgenography, ultrasound examination (UUT), echocardiography (ExoKG), elitrocardiagraphy (ECG), densitometry methods in order to determine the diagnosis and severity of this disease, taking into account the importance in these diseases, such as intrumental examination methods. The principle of these verification methods, the implementation and the aparatlar used are correct, so we did not find it necessary to dwell on them, since the information is presented in Chapter II.

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